

Elastothermodynamic Damping in Metal-Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT

When a composite material is subjected to a stress field (homogeneous or inhomogeneous), different phases undergo different temperature fluctuations due to the Thomson effect [1]. As a result irreversible heat conduction occurs, and entropy is produced. This entropy production is the genesis of elastothermodynamic damping. This damping is calculated for an N -layered medium of finite extent in a rectangular, cylindrical, and spherical coordinate system. The medium may be subjected to any loading provided the consequential heat conduction can be described by a single spatial coordinate orthogonal to the layering. By way of illustration, results are presented for (1) a periodic medium with a two-layer representative volume element, (2) a fiber in a finite matrix, and (3) a spherical inclusion in a finite matrix.

Keywords: specific damping capacity, attenuation, internal friction, elastothermodynamic, composite, fiber, spherical inclusion, entropy, heat conduction, Second Law of Thermodynamics.

1. Introduction

Whenever a solid is stressed adiabatically, there is an accompanying change in temperature; this phenomenon is known as the Thomson effect [1]. Thus, the temperature and mechanical fields are coupled, and in a vibrating structure, inhomogeneities in stress and material properties will result in inhomogeneities in temperature. Heat will conduct from the high temperature regions to the low temperature regions, and as a consequence of the Second Law of Thermodynamics, entropy is produced which is manifested as a conversion of mechanical energy into heat; this process is known as elastothermodynamic damping¹. From the viewpoint of vibration suppression in large, flexible space structures, passive damping is a critically important material property. Metal-matrix composites are a prime candidate for such structures. It is imperative, therefore, that we develop a theory for predicting elastothermodynamic damping in composite materials.

Elastothermodynamic damping was first analyzed by Zener [3-5]. He considered the transverse

¹We propose that *elastothermodynamic* is a more appropriate qualifier for the word damping than *thermoelastic*. Historically [2], the word *thermoelastic* has been used to connote a situation where the cause is an externally applied temperature field (*thermo*), and the effect is an elastic stress field (*elastic*), hence *thermoelastic*. In the present context of damping, there is no externally applied temperature field. Instead, the cause is an externally applied traction field and the accompanying stress field (*elasto*), and the effect is a temperature field (*thermo*). Moreover, the dissipation of mechanical energy occurs only if the stress field is time dependent (*dynamic*), hence *elastothermodynamic*.

vibrations of a homogeneous Euler-Bernoulli beam. Chadwick [6], Alblas [7,8], and Biot [9] extended Zener's analysis of a beam to that of a general homogeneous medium. The elastothermodynamic damping of homogeneous plates, shells, and Timoshenko beams has been investigated by various authors (Tasi, [10]; Tasi and Herrmann, [11]; Shieh, [12-14]; Lee, [15]). The elastothermodynamic damping of waves in homogeneous media has been studied by Lücke [16], Deresiewicz [17], and Gillis [18]. Goodman, et.al. [19] and Landau and Lifshitz [20] have shown that for the purpose of calculating elastothermodynamic damping, the elastothermodynamic field problem can be reduced to (1) solving the elastic field problem, (2) solving for the temperature field using the one-way coupled heat conduction equation, and (3) calculating the damping using the Second Law of Thermodynamics. Armstrong [21] used this approach to calculate the elastothermodynamic damping of a one-dimensional composite consisting of a succession of slabs under the assumption that the thermal conductivity and specific heat are invariant from slab to slab. More recently Kinra and Milligan [22] presented a Second Law analysis of the elastothermodynamic damping for two cases: (1) an interface of two materials in perfect thermal contact, and (2) a single linear inclusion in an infinite matrix [23]. Bishop and Kinra [24] used the method of Kinra and Milligan [21] to solve for the elastothermodynamic damping of a laminated beam in flexure and extension.

In this work the method of Kinra and Milligan [21] is used to obtain an analytical expression for the elastothermodynamic damping of an N -layered medium of finite extent in a rectangular, cylindrical, and spherical coordinate system (i.e. an N -layered slab, cylinder, and sphere). The medium may be subjected to any admissible stress field provided the consequential heat conduction can be described by a single spatial coordinate orthogonal to the layering. The solution for the following composites may be obtained as a special case of this general solution. *Rectangular slabs*: laminated composite in bending and extension, aligned platelet composite [25], or a periodic array of rectangular slabs. *Layered cylinder*: unidirectional fiber reinforced metal-matrix composite. *Layered sphere*: particulate composite; damping of the earth treated as a layered medium [26]. A detailed presentation of the analytical results is beyond the scope of this brief paper. However, by way of illustration, numerical results are presented for the following canonical problems which are special cases of the general N -layer development: (1) a periodic medium with a two-layer representative volume element (RVE), (2) a fiber in a finite matrix, and (3) a spherical inclusion in a finite matrix.

2. General Theory for Elastothermodynamic Damping

A complete set of field equations required to calculate the elastothermodynamic damping have been discussed in detail by Kinra and Milligan [22]. The pertinent equations are reproduced below. One-way coupled heat conduction equation:

$$\nabla^2 T - \frac{\rho C}{k} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\alpha}{k} T_o \frac{\partial \sigma_{kk}}{\partial t}, \quad (1)$$

where T is the absolute temperature, T_o is the thermodynamic equilibrium temperature and also the reference temperature at which all the material properties are taken, t is time, ρ is the mass density, α is the coefficient of thermal expansion, k is the thermal conductivity, and C is the specific heat per unit mass. Rate of entropy produced per unit mass due to irreversible heat conduction, \dot{s}_p :

$$\dot{s}_p = \frac{k}{\rho T_o^2} \nabla T \cdot \nabla T, \quad (2)$$

Rate of dissipation of mechanical energy per unit volume due to entropy production, \dot{W} [27]:

$$\dot{W} = \rho T_o \dot{s}_p, \quad (3)$$

It is now assumed that the stress field is time-harmonic with a circular frequency, ω . Let W be the maximum elastic stored energy density during a cycle,

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{lm} \epsilon_{lm} = \frac{1}{2E} \left[(1+\nu) \sigma_{lm} \sigma_{lm} - \nu \sigma_{kk}^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

where σ_{lm} is the stress tensor, ϵ_{lm} is the strain tensor, E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio. Let ΔW

be the mechanical energy dissipated during one cycle of vibration,

$$\Delta W = \oint \dot{W} dt . \quad (5)$$

A normalized measure of the rate of dissipation of mechanical energy is introduced as,

$$\dot{\psi} = \frac{\dot{W}}{\bar{W}} , \quad (6)$$

where \bar{W} is an average of W over some finite volume, V , which will be chosen as appropriate,

$$\bar{W} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V W dV . \quad (7)$$

A *local* specific damping capacity, ψ , is defined as the energy dissipated in one cycle normalized by \bar{W} ,

$$\psi = \frac{\Delta W}{\bar{W}} . \quad (8)$$

Finally, a specific damping capacity (SDC) averaged over the volume of an RVE is defined as

$$\Psi = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \psi dV . \quad (9)$$

Since the elastic stress field, which drives the temperature field, is assumed to be time-harmonic, by virtue of the principle of causality, T will also be time-harmonic; it is noted that all field equations are linear. It is emphasized that in general T will be out of phase with σ_{kk} . Let $T_o^* \equiv T_o(2)^{1/2} e^{i\pi/4}$, then the temperature field can be written as

$$T^*(\underline{r}, t) = T_o^* + V^*(\underline{r}, \omega) e^{i\omega t} , \quad (10)$$

where \underline{r} is the position vector and the superscript $()^*$ implies a complex quantity. Note that the term $V^* e^{i\omega t}$ represents the fluctuations of temperature about its equilibrium value of T_o^* . In summary, the major steps needed to calculate damping are: (I) Use Eqs. (1) and Eq. (10) to calculate V^* ; (II) Use Eqs. (2), (3), and (5) to calculate ΔW ; (III) Use Eqs. (4) and (7) to calculate \bar{W} ; and (IV) Use Eqs. (8) and (9) to calculate ψ and Ψ , respectively.

3. Damping of an N -Layered Medium

The boundary value problem of one-dimensional heat conduction for an N -layer composite region in the rectangular, cylindrical, and spherical coordinate systems (see Figure 1) has been solved by Özişik [28] using the integral transform technique. The medium may be subjected to any loading provided the consequential heat conduction can be described by a single spatial coordinate orthogonal to the layering. The inhomogeneous term of Eq. (1), due to the elastothermodynamic effect [1], may be treated as a heat generation term and solved accordingly. The solution is a series of orthogonal functions which depend only upon the material properties of each layer, the type of symmetry (rectangular, cylindrical, spherical), and boundary conditions. Once the temperature field has been calculated, the entropy produced and damping can be calculated as outlined in the previous section. These calculations are quite lengthy and beyond the scope of this paper. However, numerical results will be presented for three canonical problems (one in each of the three coordinate systems) which are special cases of the general N -layer development. In all three cases, we consider two matrix materials (Indium and Tin) and three inclusion materials (graphite and two ceramics, SiC and TiC).

I. *Cartesian Coordinates.* Consider a periodic array of two materials subjected to a uniaxial stress

perpendicular to the layering. The unit cell is shown in Figure 2a. The volume fraction of the inclusion, V_f , for this problem is the ratio a/b . The damping results are shown in Figure 3 as a function of the nondimensional frequency, Ω , ($\Omega \equiv \omega\tau$, where τ is a characteristic time of heat conduction for the first layer of the unit cell) for $T_o = 300\text{ K}$ and $V_f = 50\%$. As Ω approaches zero, heat has sufficient time to conduct and we obtain nearly isothermal conditions. Thus, the temperature gradients are nearly zero, and therefore, the entropy produced and damping goes to zero. As Ω approaches infinity, heat has insufficient time to conduct and the problem is essentially adiabatic. Since little heat is conducted the entropy produced and thus damping go to zero. The effect of volume fraction of the inclusion is shown in Figure 4, where $\zeta = a/b$. As expected the damping is zero for $\zeta = 0$ and $\zeta = 1$, since there is only one phase present and subsequently no heat conduction. The maximum value of Ψ depends upon the material combination and frequency of vibration.

II. *Cylindrical Coordinates.* Next, we consider damping of fiber-reinforced metal-matrix composites. A canonical problem is a single fiber of radius a surrounded by a concentric cylinder of matrix phase of radius b (see Figure 2b). The ratio of the two radii is chosen to reflect the volume fraction of the fibers in the actual composite. For convenience it is assumed that at $r = b$, adiabatic conditions exist. The results are presented in Figure 5 as a function of the nondimensional frequency, Ω , for the case of a uniform radial loading and a fiber volume fraction of 50% and $T_o = 300\text{ K}$. It is noted that the highest damping for the cases given is for the ceramic fiber. The damping for the previous problem but with a uniform strain applied parallel to the axis is shown in Figure 6. The damping is very small for the material combinations presented, since for this case a large amount of energy is stored in the fiber [29]. These results are consistent with the experimental findings of Wren and Kinra [30].

III. *Spherical Coordinates.* Finally, consider elastothermodynamic damping in spherical-particulate composites. A canonical problem is that of a single sphere of radius a embedded in a matrix of radius b (see Figure 2c) such that the volume fraction of the inclusion corresponds to the volume fraction of the inclusions in the actual composite. The assemblage is subjected to a uniform hydrostatic stress at $r = b$. The results are shown in Figure 7 again for an inclusion volume fraction of 50% and $T_o = 300\text{ K}$. The earlier remarks for the previous composites also apply here.

Conclusions

Recently we reported a theory for calculating the elastothermodynamic damping taking the Second Law of Thermodynamics as a starting point. In this paper, this theory has been used to calculate the elastothermodynamic damping of a rather general class of metal-matrix composites: an N -layered medium in Cartesian, cylindrical, or spherical coordinates. The MMC can be subjected to a reasonably general stress field provided it satisfies the following constraint: the heat conduction should be describable in terms of a single spatial coordinate perpendicular to the interfaces. Results are presented for three canonical problems (one in each of the three coordinate systems considered): (1) a periodic array of slabs; (2) a fiber surrounded by a finite concentric matrix cylinder; and (3) a spherical inclusion surrounded by a finite concentric matrix sphere.

High damping is achieved whenever the inclusion is made up of graphite or a ceramic embedded in a high-conductivity metal-matrix.

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Figure 1. An N -layered slab (a), cylinder (b), and sphere (c).

Figure 2. (a) unit cell of a two material periodic layered composite, (b) concentric cylinders, and (c) concentric spheres.

Figure 3. Elastothermodynamic damping of a periodic layered composite with a two layer unit cell, as a function of a nondimensional frequency, Ω , for an inclusion volume fraction of 50% and a reference temperature of 300 K.

Figure 4. Elastothermodynamic damping of a periodic layered composite with a two layer unit cell, as a function of a nondimensional frequency, Ω , and dimension ratio a/b (see Figure 2a), and a reference temperature of 300 K.

Figure 5. Elastothermodynamic damping of a fiber embedded in a concentric cylinder of matrix, under a uniform radial load, as a function of a nondimensional frequency, Ω , for a fiber volume fraction of 50%, and a reference temperature of 300 K.

Figure 6. Elastothermodynamic damping of a fiber embedded in a concentric cylinder of matrix, under a uniform axial strain, as a function of a nondimensional frequency, Ω , for a fiber volume fraction of 50%, and a reference temperature of 300 K.

Figure 7. Elastothermodynamic damping of a spherical inclusion embedded in a concentric sphere of matrix, under a uniform hydrostatic stress, as a function of a nondimensional frequency, Ω , for an inclusion volume fraction of 50%, and a reference temperature of 300 K.